

SHORTEST DISTANCE IN MODULAR CUBIC POLYNOMIALS

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Abstract

In this paper, we study how small a box contains at least two points from a modular cubic polynomial $y \equiv ax^3 + cx + d \pmod{p}$ with $(a, p) = 1$. We prove that some square of side length $p^{1/6+\epsilon}$ contains two such points.

1. Introduction and Main Results

In the x - y plane, the most common way to define distance between two points is

$$d = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}.$$

We say that two points are close to one another if d is small. However, if we are working with curves \pmod{p} , we may not be able to take the square root. So, instead of using distance, we say that two points are close to each other if they are both inside a box

$$B(X, Y; H) := \{(x, y) : X+1 \leq x \leq X+H \pmod{p}, Y+1 \leq y \leq Y+H \pmod{p}\}$$

for some X and Y with H small. We may say, in some sense, that the smallest such H is the “distance” between the two points. Here and throughout the paper, p stands for a prime number.

Recently, the author [1] studied the apparently new question of shortest “distance” in a modular hyperbola $xy \equiv c \pmod{p}$ and its relation with the least quadratic nonresidue modulo p . Inspired by this, we try to study the shortest “distance” for other kinds of curves.

For linear polynomials, the shortest distance can have order of magnitude \sqrt{p} which is optimal. For example, take $H = \lfloor \sqrt{p} \rfloor$ and $m = H + 1$. Then the numbers mh for $1 \leq h \leq H - 1$ are all greater than H and less than p . Thus, when we look at the linear equation $y \equiv mx \pmod{p}$, it cannot have two points in the box $B(X, Y, H)$. For if (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) are two such points with $1 \leq x_1 < x_2 < p$,

say $x_2 = x_1 + h$ for some $1 \leq h < H$. Then $y_2 - y_1 = mx_2 - mx_1 = mh$ cannot be any number between 1 and $H - 1 \pmod{p}$. Hence there can be no such two points from the line in the box. As for why \sqrt{p} is optimal, by any $1 \leq a \leq p$, two of $ak_1 \pmod{p}$ and $ak_2 \pmod{p}$ must be within $H + 1$ from one another for some $1 \leq k_1 < k_2 \leq H + 1$ by pigeonhole principle. So the two points (k_1, ak_1) and (k_2, ak_2) on the line $y \equiv ax \pmod{p}$ are in a box of length $H + 1$.

Meanwhile the shortest distance can be as small as $O(1)$ for quadratic polynomials. Suppose $p > 3$. Starting from any quadratic polynomial $y \equiv ax^2 + bx + c \pmod{p}$, we can turn it to the form $y \equiv ax^2 \pmod{p}$ after completing the square as shifting does not affect distance. Now, consider the two points (x_1, ax_1^2) and (x_2, ax_2^2) with $a(2x_1 + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ and $x_2 = x_1 + 1$. One can verify that they are both in the box $B(x_1 - 1, ax_1^2 - 1; 2)$.

Next, we study the shortest distance for the next type of curves, namely cubic polynomials. It turns out that this can be studied perfectly with the method of [1].

Let $p > 3$ be a prime, $(a, p) = 1$, and c any integer. We consider the reduced modular cubic polynomial

$$C_{a,c} := \{(x, y) : y \equiv ax^3 + cx \pmod{p}\}.$$

The restriction to such reduced cubic polynomials is not restrictive at all as one can transform a general cubic to such form through change of variables in x and y which does not affect the distance between points on the cubic polynomial. We consider how small a box $B(X, Y; H)$ contains at least two points in $C_{a,c}$ where X and Y run through $0, 1, \dots, p - 1$. To study this, we need a recent result of Heath-Brown [2] and Shao [3] on mean-value estimates of character sums:

Theorem 1. *Given $H \leq p$, a positive integer and any $\epsilon > 0$. Suppose that $0 \leq N_1 < N_2 < \dots < N_J < p$ are integers satisfying $N_{j+1} - N_j \geq H$ for $1 \leq j < J$. Then*

$$\sum_{j=1}^J \max_{h \leq H} |S(N_j; h)|^{2r} \ll_{\epsilon, r} H^{2r-2} p^{1/2+1/(2r)+\epsilon}$$

where

$$S(N; H) := \sum_{N < n \leq N+H} \chi(n)$$

and χ is any non-principal character modulo p .

Applying the above theorem, we can show that

Theorem 2. *For any $\epsilon > 0$, for any $(a, p) = 1$, integer c and $H \gg_{\epsilon} p^{1/6+\epsilon}$, we have*

$$|C_{a,c} \cap B(X, Y; H)| \geq 2$$

for some $0 \leq X, Y \leq p - 1$.

As a consequence, we also have the following curious new results.

Corollary 1. *For any $\epsilon > 0$ and integer c , there exist $1 \leq u_1, v_1, u_2, v_2 \ll_\epsilon p^{1/6+\epsilon}$ such that*

$$\left(\frac{u_1}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u_1^3 + cu_1 - v_1}{p}\right) = 1$$

and

$$\left(\frac{u_2}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u_2^3 + cu_2 - v_2}{p}\right) = -1.$$

In particular, by setting $c = 0$, we have

$$\left(\frac{u_3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u_3^3 - v_3}{p}\right) = 1$$

and

$$\left(\frac{u_4}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u_4^3 - v_4}{p}\right) = -1$$

for some $1 \leq u_3, v_3, u_4, v_4 \ll_\epsilon p^{1/6+\epsilon}$.

Finally, we finish with the following

Conjecture 1. For any $\epsilon > 0$, for any $(a, p) = 1$, integer c and $H \gg_\epsilon p^\epsilon$, we have

$$|C_{a,c} \cap B(X, Y; H)| \geq 2$$

for some $0 \leq X, Y \leq p - 1$.

Some Notation. Throughout the paper, p stands for a prime. The symbol $|S|$ denotes the number of elements in the set S . We also use the Legendre symbol $\left(\frac{\cdot}{p}\right)$. The notations $f(x) \ll g(x)$, $g(x) \gg f(x)$ and $f(x) = O(g(x))$ are equivalent to $|f(x)| \leq Cg(x)$ for some constant $C > 0$. Finally, $f(x) \ll_{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k} g(x)$, $g(x) \gg_{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k} f(x)$ and $f(x) = O_{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k}(g(x))$ mean that the implicit constant C may depend on $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k$.

2. The Basic Argument

Without loss of generality, we assume that $p > 3$. For $(a, p) = 1$ and any integer c , suppose $|C_{a,c} \cap B(X, Y; H)| \geq 2$ for some $0 \leq X, Y \leq p - 1$. This means that

$$y \equiv ax^3 + cx \pmod{p}, \text{ and } y + v \equiv a(x + u)^3 + c(x + u) \pmod{p} \quad (1)$$

for some $1 \leq x, y \leq p$ and $1 \leq u, v \leq H$. Subtracting, we get

$$v \equiv 3au(x^2 + ux + \bar{3}u^2) + cu \pmod{p}$$

where \bar{y} denotes the multiplicative inverse of y modulo p (i.e. $y\bar{y} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$.) After some algebra and completing the square, we have

$$(2x + u)^2 \equiv 4\bar{3}v\bar{a}u - \bar{3}u^2 - 4\bar{3}\bar{a}c \pmod{p}.$$

The above process is reversible. So $|C_{a,c} \cap B(X, Y; H)| \geq 2$ for some $0 \leq X, Y \leq p-1$ is equivalent to

$$\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u}{p}\right)\left(\frac{au^3 + 4cu - 4v}{p}\right) = 1.$$

We are going to restrict our attention to even $u = 2u'$'s and $v = 2v'$'s. So we want

$$\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u'}{p}\right)\left(\frac{au'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) = 1 \text{ for some } 1 \leq u', v' \leq H/2. \tag{2}$$

3. Proofs of Theorem 2 and Corollary 1

Proof. Suppose (2) is not true. Then either

$$\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u'}{p}\right)\left(\frac{au'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) = 0;$$

or

$$\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u'}{p}\right)\left(\frac{au'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) = -1$$

for all $1 \leq u', v' \leq H/2$. If the former is true for two pairs of $1 \leq u', v' \leq H/2$, we have

$$au'^3 + cu' \equiv v' \pmod{p} \text{ and } au''^3 + cu'' \equiv v'' \pmod{p} \tag{3}$$

which gives Theorem 2. Henceforth we suppose the latter is true for all but at most one pair of $1 \leq u', v' \leq H/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} H^2 &\ll \left| \sum_{u' \leq H/2} \sum_{v' \leq H/2} \left(\frac{u'}{p}\right)\left(\frac{au'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) \right| \leq \sum_{u' \leq H/2} \left| \sum_{v' \leq H/2} \left(\frac{au'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) \right| \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{u' \leq H/2} 1 \right)^{(2r-1)/(2r)} \left(\sum_{u' \leq H/2} \left| \sum_{v' \leq H/2} \left(\frac{au'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) \right|^{2r} \right)^{1/(2r)}. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose $|C_{a,c} \cap B(X, Y; H)| \leq 1$ for all $0 \leq X, Y \leq p-1$. Then the points $au'^3 + cu'$ are spaced more than H apart. So we can apply Theorem 1 and get

$$H^2 \ll_{\epsilon,r} H^{(2r-1)/(2r)} (H^{2r-2} p^{1/2+1/(2r)+\epsilon})^{1/(2r)}$$

which gives $H \ll_{\epsilon,r} p^{(r+1)/(6r)+\epsilon/2}$. This contradicts $H \gg_{\epsilon} p^{1/6+\epsilon}$ if r is sufficiently large. This final contradiction together with (3) gives Theorem 2. \square

Proof. By setting $a = 1$, the above proof gives some $1 \leq u', v' \ll_{\epsilon} p^{1/6+\epsilon}$ such that

$$\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u'}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u'^3 + cu' - v'}{p}\right) = 1.$$

A similar argument also gives some $1 \leq u'', v'' \ll_{\epsilon} p^{1/6+\epsilon}$ such that

$$\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u''}{p}\right)\left(\frac{u''^3 + cu'' - v''}{p}\right) = -1.$$

It follows that Corollary 1 is true. \square

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